

Prevalence and Antimicrobial Susceptibility Pattern of Citrobacter Species with Special Reference to ESBL Production, Isolated from Different Samples from a Tertiary Care Hospital in Bihar

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Abstract:

Introduction: Citrobacter species is gram negative, enteric bacilli that colonize in moist environment and found mostly in water, soil, food, and the intestines of animals and humans. They cause a wide spectrum of infections involving the urinary tract, liver, biliary tract, peritoneum, intestines, one, respiratory tract, endocardium, wounds, soft tissue, meninges, and the bloodstream. Increasing resistance to beta-lactam drugs especially the 3rd-generation cephalosporin in Citrobacter species is predominantly due to the production of multidrug resistant enzymes in particular extended spectrum beta-lactamases (ESBLs).

Material & Method: This was a hospital lab based observational study carried out from the 500 samples, - 100 from each sample type (100 Urine, 100 Pus, 100 Sputum, 100 Blood and 100 Body fluid) collected over a period of 6 months from 13-08-2022 to 23-02-2023 at NMCH, Patna Bihar. Among these processed samples positive isolates of Citrobacter species are recovered and for further study sent to the department of Microbiology. First find out Antimicrobial susceptibility pattern and ESBL producing strain from isolated Citrobacter species then find out total prevalence and ESBL, non-ESBL prevalence. Antimicrobial susceptibility pattern tested against different antibiotics and determine the antibiogram of these isolates. ESBL production in all these isolates are detected by using double disc synergy test (DDST).

Result: Out of 500 samples, 44 (8.80%) were detected positive for Citrobacter species isolates. Out of these 44 clinical isolates of Citrobacter species recruited for this study, 26 isolates (i.e. 59%) were confirmed to be ESBL producers by the DDST method and rest 18 (41%) non-ESBL producer. AST pattern shows high resistance rate to Cefotaxime, Cotrimoxazole, Ciprofloxacin, Gentamycin and more sensitive to Imipenem and with Colistin no resistant found in this study.

Conclusion: From our results, it could be deduced that 59% of Citrobacter isolates harbour or express ESBLs; and they are resistant to commonly used antibiotics inclusive of some beta-lactams and non-beta-lactam antibiotics. There is therefore need for proper AST monitoring and detection of resistant antibiotics from clinically important bacterial pathogens so as to guide therapy and to contain their nefarious effect.

Keywords: Citrobacter Species, Antimicrobial Susceptibility Pattern, ESBL, Imipenem.

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Introduction

The genus Citrobacter in the Enterobacteriaceae family consists of 13 currently recognized species, and among these, Citrobacter freundii and Citrobacter koseri are the most frequently associated with infection of humans [1]. They are frequently found in water, soil, food, and the intestines of animals and humans. Previously recognized as environmental contaminants or colonizers with low virulence, they are now known to cause a wide spectrum of infections involving the urinary tract, liver, biliary tract, peritoneum,

intestines, bone, respiratory tract, endocardium, wounds, soft tissue, meninges, and the bloodstream [1,2,3,4]. Citrobacter species account for 0.8% of all Gram-negative infections in one large observational study and have represented approximately 3.6% of the isolates of Enterobacteriaceae in a hospital setting [2,5,6]. Citrobacter infection can occur in sporadic cases or as nosocomial spread. Documented outbreaks in the ward or intensive care unit (ICU) resulted in colonization, surgical wound infection, and

meningitis. Therefore, a well-established hospital policy is essential for infection control [7,8,9]. A mortality rate of 6.8% has been reported among hospitalized patients with *Citrobacter* infections, but it can significantly increase to 17.8- 56% with *Citrobacter* bacteremia [10,11,12].

Public concern has risen in regard with longer hospital stays and higher antibiotic costs due to the recent emergence of multidrug-resistant strains of *Citrobacter*. Multidrug-resistant strains of *Citrobacter* are more commonly acquired among patients who have received previous antibiotic treatments, and this fact results from the inducible expression of Amp-C and the selection of ESBL strains [10,13]. Multidrug-resistant *C. freundii* strains have been associated with a higher rate of in-hospital mortality compared to susceptible strains [14].

Urinary tract infection (UTI) continues to be the commonest nosocomial infection and approximately 40% of all hospital acquired infections and it is one of the most important causes of morbidity and mortality [15]. UTIs caused by *Citrobacter* species have been described in 5 to 12% of bacterial urine isolates in adults [16].

Although serious septicemias in neonatal patients have been reported, bacteremia due to *Citrobacter* is less common in adults. Bloodstream infection of *Citrobacter* in adults can originate from the abdominal cavity, the urinary tract, lungs, or intravascular catheters [8,17].

This hospital based prospective study has been conducted to provide information regarding the MDR status and ESBL production of this emerging pathogen of medical interest.

Material & Methods

Type of Study: This was a hospital lab based observational study. *Citrobacter* species isolates are recovered from different sample (Urine, Pus, Sputum, Blood, Body fluid) collected at culture collection unit (Central lab, Microbiology) and sent to department for further study.

Period of study: Study conducted from August 2022 to February 2023 (6 months).

Sample Size: 500 samples, - 100 from each sample type (100 Urine, 100 Pus, 100 Blood, 100 Body-fluid and 100 Sputum) taken in the study

Place of study: Department of Microbiology, NMCH PATNA.

Age: No age specification.

Gender: No gender specification.

Methodology

Citrobacter species isolates are recovered from different sample (Urine, Pus, Sputum, Blood, Body fluid) collected at culture collection unit (Central lab, Microbiology) and sent to department. First we done Antimicrobial susceptibility testing then find out which strain of *Citrobacter* species are ESBL producing.

Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (AST):

Isolated *Citrobacter* species are tested against different antibiotics and commonly used discs are - Cefotaxime (30 µg), Ciprofloxacin (5 µg), Colistin (10 µg), Cotrimoxazole (Trimethoprim-sulfa methoxazole 1.25/23.75 µg), Gentamicin (10 µg), Imipenem (10 µg). For urine sample we also used Nitrofurantoin 300 µg for better concentrate in urinary system. Zone of inhibition was recorded as "Sensitive" or "Resistant" according to the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI)-2022 guideline [18]. *Citrobacter* species intrinsic resistant [22] to - Ampicillin, Ampicillin-subactam, Amoxicillin-clavunate, Cefazolin, Cephalothin, Cefotetam, Cefoxitin, Cefuroxime.

So these antibiotics not used in our study.

Antibiotic susceptibility of isolates was done on Muller Hinton agar using Kirby Bauer method (Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute [CLSI]). Antibiotic discs were obtained from HiMedia, Mumbai, India. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 27853 and *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923 were used as controls. MDR was defined as resistance for >3 class of antibiotics.

ESBL Production: ESBL productions in all these isolates were detected by double disc synergy test.

Double Disc Test:

A standard 0.5 McFarland inoculum of Bacteria is plated on Muller Hinton agar and discs of Ceftazidime (30 µg), Cefotaxim (30 µg) and Ceftazidime-clavulunate (30/10 µg), Cefotaxim-clavulunate (30/10 µg) is placed at a distance of 20 mm and incubated at 37°C for 18 hrs.

A 5mm increase in a zone diameter for either antimicrobial agent tested in combination with clavulunate vs the zone diameter of the agent when tested alone is considered as ESBL production.

Escherichia coli ATCC 25922 used as a negative control for the ESBL and *P. aeruginosa* ATCC 27853 was used as a control strain for a positive ESBL.

Results

Table 1: No. of Citrobacter isolates and ESBL producers among isolates studied

SL No.	Sample type (n=500)	No. of Citrobacter isolates (n=44)	No. of ESBL positive isolates n=26 (59%)
1.	Urine (n=100)	16 (16%)	n=16, 11 (68.75%)
2.	Pus (n=100)	11 (11%)	n=11, 06 (54.54%)
3.	Blood (n=100)	08 (8%)	n=08, 05 (62.50%)
4.	Body fluids (n=100)	06 (6%)	n=06, 03 (50.50%)
5.	Sputum (n=100)	03 (3%)	n=03, 01 (33.33%)

Figure 1: Comparison of Sensitivity pattern between ESBL & NON-ESBL Citrobacter isolates with different antibiotics

Figure 2: Distribution of Citrobacter isolates according to ESBL production

Table 2: Sensitivity and Resistant pattern of Citrobacter isolates from urine sample n= 16

Antibiotics	Number of Sensitive Citrobacter Strains (Percentage) (n = 16)	Number of Resistant Citrobacter Strains (Percentage) (n = 16)
Ciprofloxacin	9 (56.25%)	7 (43.75%)
Cotrimoxazole	10 (62.50%)	6 (37.50%)
Gentamycin	11 (68.75%)	5 (31.25%)
Cefotaxime	6 (37.50%)	10 (62.50%)
Imipenem	13 (81.25%)	3 (18.75%)
Nitrofurantoin	6 (37.50%)	10 (62.50%)
Colistin	16 (100%)	0 (0%)

Table 3: Sensitivity and Resistant pattern of Citrobacter isolates from pus sample n=11

Antibiotics	Number of Sensitive Citrobacter Strains (Percentage) (n = 11)	Number of Resistant Citrobacter Strains (Percentage) (n = 11)
Ciprofloxacin	6 (54.54%)	5 (45.45%)
Cotrimoxazole	7 (63.63%)	4 (36.36%)
Gentamycin	8 (72.72%)	3 (27.27%)
Cefotaxime	5 (45.45%)	6 (54.54%)
Imipenem	9 (81.81%)	2 (18.18%)
Colistin	11 (100%)	0 (0%)

Table 4: Sensitivity and Resistant pattern of Citrobacter isolates from blood n=8

Antibiotics	Number of Sensitive Citrobacter Strains (Percentage) (n = 8)	Number of Resistant Citrobacter Strains (Percentage) (n = 8)
Ciprofloxacin	4 (50.00%)	4 (50.00%)
Cotrimoxazole	4 (50.00%)	4 (50.00%)
Gentamycin	5 (62.50%)	3 (37.50%)
Cefotaxime	3 (37.50%)	5 (62.50%)
Imipenem	6 (75.00%)	2 (25.00%)
Colistin	8 (100%)	0 (0%)

Table 5: Sensitivity and Resistant pattern of Citrobacter isolates from body-fluid n=6

Antibiotics	Number of Sensitive Citrobacter Strains (Percentage) (n = 6)	Number of Resistant Citrobacter Strains (Percentage) (n = 6)
Ciprofloxacin	2 (33.33%)	4 (66.66%)
Cotrimoxazole	3 (50.00%)	3 (50.00%)
Gentamycin	4 (66.66%)	2 (33.33%)
Cefotaxime	3 (50.00%)	3 (50.00%)
Imipenem	5 (83.33%)	1 (16.66%)
Colistin	6 (100%)	0 (0%)

Table 6: Sensitivity and Resistant pattern of Citrobacter isolates from sputum sample n=3

Antibiotics	Number of Sensitive Citrobacter Strains (Percentage) (n = 3)	Number of Resistant Citrobacter Strains (Percentage) (n = 3)
Ciprofloxacin	0 (0%)	3 (100%)
Cotrimoxazole	1 (33.33%)	2 (66.66%)
Gentamycin	2 (66.66%)	1 (33.33%)
Cefotaxime	1 (33.33%)	2 (66.66%)
Imipenem	3 (100%)	0 (0%)
Colistin	3 (100%)	0 (0%)

Table 7: Sensitivity and Resistant pattern of ESBL & NON-ESBL Citrobacter isolates with different antibiotics

Antibiotics (for all samples)	Number of strains(Percentage)					
	ESBL (n = 26)			NON-ESBL (n = 18)		
	S	I	R	S	I	R
Ciprofloxacin	8(30.77%)		18 (69.23%)	13(72.22%)		5 (27.78%)
Cotrimoxazole	11(42.30%)		15 (57.69%)	14(77.78%)		4 (22.22%)

Gentamycin	15(57.69%)		11(42.30%)	15(83.33%)		3 (16.67%)
Cefotaxime	5(19.23%)		21 (80.77%)	13(72.22%)		5 (27.78%)
Imipenem	20(76.92%)	1	6 (23.07%)	16(88.89%)		2 (11.11%)
Colistin	26(100%)		0 (0%)	18(100%)		0 (0%)
Antibiotics (for urine samples)	ESBL (n = 11)			NON-ESBL (n = 5)		
	S	I	R	S	I	R
Nitrofurantoin	2(18.18%)		9 (81.82%)	4(80%)		1(20%)

Figure 3: Comparison of Sensitivity pattern between ESBL & NON-ESBL Citrobacter isolates with different antibiotics

Discussion

Our study focused on the overall prevalence and antimicrobial susceptibility pattern comparative with ESBL strains of Citrobacter species in a tertiary care hospital. According to the present study, the overall prevalence of Citrobacter species was 8.80% with highest in urine sample (16%) followed by pus (11%), blood (8%), body fluid (6%) and lowest in sputum (3%). Various studies have reported 1% to 8.23% as the prevalence rate of Citrobacter spp [19]. Our study is in accordance with another study by Poonam AR et al [20]. In 2019 in which prevalence rate of Citrobacter spp.

was 2.4% with highest in urine sample (56%) followed by pus (21.6%), sputum (8.4%) and lowest in blood (7.2%). A study by Avinash et al [21]. Mentioned the results of Citrobacter species, 150 (59.76%) were from urine, 60(23.9%) from Pus, 8(7.17%) from blood, 16(6.37%) from Sputum in which prevalence rate was higher than this study.

Our results presented approx. 59% ESBL production among all Citrobacter isolates which is higher than values reported 41% in other studies in India by Mary Dhason et al [22]. in 202222. In general, there is a considerable geographic difference in the prevalence of ESBLs in different

countries. The emergence of resistance in *Citrobacter* strains that had been consistently susceptible to standard antimicrobial therapy is of growing clinical concern, as is the alarming trend to multidrug resistance. With this in mind, the early detection of ESBLs, the judicious use of appropriate antibiotics, and the implementation of infection control strategies are major concerns to avoid the spread of this threat in the hospital. In this study though the proportion of patients sensitive to imipenem was high, with approx. 20% resistant. The least sensitive antibiotic in *Citrobacter* was the 3rd generation cephalosporin-Cefotaxime. Due to the irrational use of this antibiotic most of the organisms have developed resistance over a period of time. This finding is in accordance with another study by Therese Mary Dhasanl et al [22]. in 2022. Our study reported the highest resistance rate to Cotrimoxazole, Ciprofloxacin, Gentamycin. The resistance to imipenems was 20%, results from reduced levels of drug accumulation or increased expression of pump efflux or production of ESBL. Carbapenems are considered to be the treatment of choice against serious ESBL associated infections. According to the present study imipenem is a promising drug in the isolates from urine, pus, body-fluid, and blood samples as well. Second antibiotic of choice was Gentamycin and Colistin as a reserved for MDR cases and last use drug.

Conclusion

Now a day trends of nosocomial pathogens in health care settings by *Citrobacter* species is increasing. The presence of ESBL in *Citrobacter* species is also increasing, which rendering many antimicrobial agents ineffective. Single-drug or multidrug resistance in *Citrobacter* species isolates is an everyday reality for laboratories and hospitals and evidence is growing regarding the ability of certain resistant clones to spread by cross-transmission. This study represents an attempt to cover resistant infections from a small evidence base and with the threat of limited new drugs in the pipeline. Although *Citrobacter* showed resistance to various antimicrobial agents were fully susceptible to Colistin in this study. The final conclusion in this study was imipenem is a primarily and first use drug in the isolates from urine, pus, body-fluid, and blood samples as well. Second antibiotic of choice is Gentamycin and Colistin is reserved for last use drug in MDR isolates. Hence, infection prevention and control practices along with judicious use of antibiotics based on the Antibiotic Policy can prevent the morbidities and mortalities due to *Citrobacter* infection.

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